

Proceedings of National Seminar

on

**INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
NORTH-EASTERN STATES**

9-10th October, 2015

**Department of Economics
Women's College, Agartala**

CONTENTS

Development of Rail-Road Infrastructure in North-East India Pranay Jyoti Goswami	1
Power Sector and Economic Growth of Tripura: A Journey to Success Haripada Datta	11
Development of Health Infrastructure in Tripura Pranay Jyoti Goswami and Satyabrata Goswami	34
Impact of Societal Infrastructure on Health, Education and Economic Well-being with special reference to NER: A Statistical Perspective Goutam Saha, Debabrata Bhattacharjee, Tapesh Ranjan Chakraborty	44
Infrastructural Status of Railway Transportation in Tripura, India: A Geographical Analysis Stabak Roy, Saptarshi Mitra	61
Hue and Cry for Sanitation Infrastructure: A Critical Review with Special Reference to Tripura Sudipta Das, Arobindo Mahato	74
The Infrastructure-Environment Nexus and Economic Development in India Rajshree Dutta	90
Exploring the Linkage between Infrastructural Growth and Entrepreneurship Development: A Study with Special Reference to Rubber Industry Sankha Pallab Chakrabarti and Debasis Neogi	102
Development of Tourism Infrastructure in India's North-Eastern Region Rupak Das	118
North-East India a Storehouse of Bio-resource and Bio-prospecting: The Treasure for Socio-Economic Development Anupam Guha	136
A Comparative Infrastructural Developmental Scenario in Rural ADC and Non-ADC Villages of South Tripura District, Tripura: A Case Study Rajib Lal Deb Barma and Saptarshi Mitra	146

Hue and Cry for Sanitation Infrastructure: A Critical Review with Special Reference to Tripura

Sudipta Das

Doctoral scholar

Dept. of Rural Management & Development, Tripura University (A Central University)

Email- sudipta1411@gmail.com, Mob- + 919774786142

Arobindo Mahato

Asst. Professor

Dept. of Rural Management & Development, Tripura University (A Central University)

Email- arobindoy@gmail.com, Mob- + 919863426466

Abstract :

Nowadays there is hue and cry on sanitation and unhygienic conditions in India. Jharkhand and Bihar is the most effected state in India with high percentages of poor sanitation facility and this issue is also neglected in Tripura. The paper highlights the present state of concerns and progress rate of sanitation facility in Tripura and also in India. This paper is qualitative in nature with narrative analysis based on secondary data. It was obviously a very important component of development since India is lacking of basic social infrastructure like roads, transport, power, water supply and sanitation, irrigation, telecommunication, education and health services, etc. in rural villages. On the other hand facts and figures of census of India, 2011 shows that still around 70 percent of India's rural and slum population (650 million) are exposed to water-borne and vector-borne diseases due to lack of basic sanitation facility and unhygienic conditions. And 60 percent of open defecation in the world is in India and rural area shares a significant part of it. The government has initiated many programmes and schemes like Central Rural Sanitation Programme, Swachh Bharat Abhiyan etc. for infrastructure development of rural areas in order to improve the standard of living of rural people. Moreover it will be efficient if the government collaborates with Public Private Partnerships (PPP) model, which can supplement the infrastructure deficit as well as sustainable development of rural areas. PPP can be profitably harnessed to reinforce India's position on the world map.

Keywords: Sanitation, Public Private Partnership, Unhygienic, Swachh Bharat Abhiyan.

1. Introduction

The role of social infrastructure for development has been well documented in the abstract. Infrastructure development, both economic and social, is one of the major determinants of the economic growth, particularly in developing countries. Sanitation is vital for human health and it is one of the important indicators that reflect the quality of life of the people. It is a basic necessity that affects everyone's life and it is a yard stick of socio-cultural and economic development of a nation. India stands second amongst the worst places in the world for sanitation.(Snehalatha, 2011). The severity of the problem in India could be judged from the fact that hardly 33% of overall population has sanitation facility available. Children especially continue to pay the price for improper sanitary conditions, in lost lives, missed schooling, in disease, malnutrition and poverty. Poor sanitation, hygiene and unsafe water claim the lives of an estimated over 1.5 million children under the age of five every year. Over one billion people worldwide have gained access to improved sanitation in the past 14 years, with the global sanitation coverage having increased from 49 per cent to 59 per cent between 1990 and 2004 (Unicef, 2008). And the world continues to be off the track to meet the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) target to reduce by half the proportion of people without access to basic sanitation by 2015. A mere 14 percent of people in rural areas of the country had access to toilets in 1990; the proportion had gone up to 28 percent in 2006. In rural areas of India, 74 percent of the population still defecates in the open. The sanitation landscape in India is still littered with 13 million unsanitary bucket latrines, which require scavengers to conduct house-to-house excreta collection. Over 700,000 Indians still make their living this way. Moreover, India is losing billions of dollars each year because of poor sanitation. Illnesses are costly to families, and to the economy as a whole in terms of productivity losses and expenditures on medicines, health care, and funerals (WaterAid India, 2012).

1.1 An introduction to Swachh Bharat Abhiyan:

To accelerate the progress of sanitation in rural areas, Government of India is implementing from 2.10.2014, the '(Swachh Bharat Abhiyan)', a Centrally Sponsored Scheme [earlier Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA)]. Similarly, to provide better sanitation facility to the rural people (Unicef, 2008).

Objectives of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan:

The main objectives of the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan are as under:

- i) To achieve 100 percent access to sanitation for all rural households by 2022.
- ii) Elimination of open defecation in India by 2019 by construction of individual, cluster & community toilets.
- iii) Conversion of unsanitary toilets to pour flush toilets (a type of pit latrine, usually connected to two pits).
- iv) Behavioural change in people regarding healthy sanitation practices. Generation of awareness among citizens about sanitation and its linkages with public health (GOI, 2011).

2. Sanitation Scenario in India:

The practice of open defecation in India comes from a combination of factors the most prominent of them being the traditional behavioral pattern and lack of awareness of people about the associated health hazards. Sanitation is a state responsibility under the Indian constitution. States may in turn bestow this responsibility to the Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRI) in rural areas or Municipalities in urban areas, called Urban Local Bodies (ULB). At present, states generally plan, design and execute water supply schemes and often operate them, through their State Departments of Public Health Engineering or Rural Development Engineering or State Water & Sanitation Boards. The national trend is to decentralize capital investment to Engineering departments at the district level and operation and maintenance to district and Gram Panchayat levels (PM News Bureau, 2008).

The first five year plans had allocated very negligible investments to sanitation while the sixth plan had considerable amount due to the launch of International Drinking Water Supply and Sanitation decade in 1980. The Ministry of Urban Development (MoUD) was the nodal agency for water and sanitation sector at the beginning of the Seventh Plan. Subsequently, rural water supply and sanitation have been transferred to the Department of Rural Development (DRD), while the administration of urban water supply and sanitation has

been retained with the MoUD. Rural water supply was an important constituent of the State sector MNP during the Seventh Plan. Rural sanitation programme was also added to the State sector MNP (Minimum Needs Program) from 1987-88. In November 1986, a new Centrally Sponsored Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) was launched. The CRSP relied on providing the hardware subsidies and not focused on other aspects resulting in just 1 percent increase of rural sanitation. The 2001 census revealed only 22 per cent of the households having access to a toilet with an investment of over 6 billion to construct 9 million toilets. Recognizing the limitations of this approach, the Total Sanitation Campaign was launched in 1999. The TSC moves away from the infrastructure focused approach of earlier programs and concentrates on promoting behavior change (GOI, 2011).

In addition, it includes a fiscal incentive scheme, Nirmal Gram Puraskar that promotes the role of Gram Panchayat and local communities in achieving community-wide total sanitation status. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, India's biggest ever cleanliness drive and the programme aims to make India "open defecation free" by 2019. A village is declared "open defecation free" if each household in the village has a fly-proof toilet and safe sewage disposal system and every member of the household has access to a toilet and 100% usage of the toilet (GOI, 2011).

3. Evolution of Schemes and programs:

i) Central Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) –

In November 1986, a new Centrally Sponsored Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) was launched. The CRSP relied on providing the hardware subsidies and not focused on other aspects resulting in just 1 percent increase of rural sanitation.

ii) Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) -

Total Sanitation Campaign programme is a comprehensive programme to ensure sanitation facilities in rural areas with broader goal to eradicate the practice of open defecation. The Central Rural Sanitation Program (CRSP) launched in 1986 and revised in 1992 was a traditional, supply-driven subsidy-oriented program. In April 1999, CRSP was restructured and launched as the Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) making it 'people

oriented' and 'demand driven'. The program is implemented in a campaign mode with the district as a unit. The total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) is one of the eight flagship programmes of the Government. TSC projects have been sanctioned in 593 rural districts of the country with a total outlay of Rs. 17,885 crore with a central share of Rs. 11,094 crore.

iii) **Nirmal Gram Puraskar (NGP)-**

To energize the TSC, the government, in 2003, initiated an incentive scheme for fully sanitized and Open-Defecation-Free (ODF) Gram Panchayats blocks and districts. The scheme was called the Nirmal Gram Puraskar, and the incentive provision is for Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) as well as individuals and organizations that are the driving force behind full sanitation coverage.

iv) **Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA)-**

Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan is a programme to ensure sanitation facilities with a goal to stop open defecation. The programme was launched on 2012.

v) **Swachh Bharat Abhiyan(SBA)-**

This campaign aims to accomplish the vision of a 'Clean India' by 2 October 2019 by elimination of open defecation, facilitating private-sector participation in capital expenditure and operation and maintenance costs for sanitary facilities, supporting urban local bodies in designing, executing and operating waste disposal systems, generation of awareness among citizens about sanitation and its linkages with public health and a behavioral change in people regarding healthy sanitation practices, Eradication of manual scavenging and 100% collection and processing/disposal/reuse/recycling of municipal solid waste.

After sluggish progress throughout the eighties and nineties, rural sanitation coverage received a fillip with the implementation of the TSC. As can be seen from Figure below, individual household latrine coverage is around 71% as of April 2011. In terms of progress made during the XI Plan, the coverage has progressively moved from 39% approximately in the beginning of the XI Plan to 72% as of May, 2011.

4. Objectives of the Study:

- i) To assess the status and condition of sanitation and hygiene facility.
- ii) To find out the progress rate and future prospective of sanitation in Tripura.

4.1 Research Methodology:

The study is based on the collection and analysis of data obtained from secondary sources. The data were collected from: Department of drinking water and sanitation, Annual report, DISE data report and Data are also collected from Census of India, 1981-2011.

5. Result & Discussion:

Figure: 1 Rural Sanitation Coverage in India

Source: 12th Five Year Plan, Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation

Figure 1 shows the rural sanitation program in India, which was first launched and started in 1980, caught full speed around 2008, after introduction of Nirmal Gram Puraskar, towards reaching its goal of bringing the desired behavioural changes for relevant sanitation practices in the country. It is evident from the figure that the program achieved success to quite a high percentage after the launch of Nirmal Gram Puraskar and it has been successful as a fiscal

incentive to motivate scaling up of rural sanitation resulting in 25,145 Gram Panchayats becoming Nirmal as one the outcomes of Total Sanitation Campaign.

Figure: 2 Year-wise Allocations and Expenditure on Sanitation in India

Source: www.ddws.nic.in date: 01:01:2010

It could be inferred from Fig 2 that from 2006 onwards the approvals got declined from the central budgets. While the budget releases declined for the year 2009-10 and consequently the expenditure causing the concern to reach the full coverage of sanitation. The decrease on allocation and expenditure causes a big concern towards the next planning phases.

Figure: 3 Component-wise percentage of financial progress In India

Source: WHO World Health Report, 2005

The detailed component wise expenditure as shown in Fig 3 reveals that except under the school sanitation and Anganwadi's toilets, the expenditure is 35% only which is an alarming situation and it raises lot of concerns over the realistic nature of the targets set to achieve. Further the reasons for the progress in school sanitation could be attributed to the fact that the funds are released to the SSA (Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan) program of Education Department for construction of the school toilets. They take up construction of school sanitary complexes as part of improving the school infrastructure and facilities. Further non provisions of toilets within the school premises were causing school dropouts especially in case of girl children hence the acceleration to complete toilet construction has gained momentum. But field reality is that the toilets constructed are not being used by children, they are either locked or not being used due to water and other cleanliness issues. The percentage of achievement with respect to Solid and Liquid waste management is lasted at India level (5%) indicating the low importance given to the task.

Figure 4 Sanitation Related Disease in India.

Source: WHO World Health Report, 2005

Figure 4 depicts the Sanitation Related Disease in India. It was observed that 37% death occur due to neonatal causes i.e. neonatal tetanus, severe infection, birth asphyxia, congenital anomalies, and etc. related diseases in children under the age of five. Then second highest is 21% i.e. Diarrhoeal Diseases and the 3rd highest is Acute Respiratory Infection i.e.19%. For this reason on an average, 30 million persons in rural areas suffer from sanitation related diseases and about 1 lakhs children in age group between 1-4 years die annually in India. Diarrhoea's impact is particularly severe in children. Acute diarrhoea, as occurs with cholera,

if left untreated can cause death within a day or less. Diarrhoeal diseases are transmitted through human excreta, and it is therefore critically important to have effective barriers in place to prevent this major transmission route. Improved sanitation alone could reduce diarrhoea-related morbidity by more than a third; improved sanitation combined with hygiene awareness and behaviors could reduce it by two thirds. Infectious diseases and diarrhoea in particular, are the main determinants of wasting and stunting of growth in children.

6. Sanitation Scenario in Tripura

Tripura has high incidence of open defecation, especially in the interior hilly and forest areas. The state has extensively implemented Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan and currently the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan and convergence with MGNREGS to address this problem. Schools and Anganwadi's Center are focused to provide with urinals and latrines, separate for boys and girls along with baby friendly toilets in Anganwadi's Centers to inculcate the habit of using sanitary latrines in young age. Many toilets lie dysfunctional due to lack of maintenance and damage. Earlier schemes of providing plastic squatting plates, free of cost to people, has not produced results as most of them lie unused as many people cannot afford to construct a toilet. Open defecation has created problems of diarrhoea and vulnerability to malaria. The Chief Minister of Tripura has envisioned making the state Open Defecation Free (ODF) by 2017 (Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation, 2014).

Table: 1 Achievement of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan & Swachh Bharat Mission

Sl. No	District Name	Households BLS-2012	Total Detail Entered (With & Without Toilet) BLS-2012	Details pending for no. of Households (not having toilet)	No. of HH covered in 2013-14 (reported in no.'s)	No. of HH entered by name [2013-14	No. of Households covered 2014-2015 (including unapproved)	Total No. of Households Covered after Survey 2012	Balance uncovered HH
1	DHALAI	93748	85225	148	400	0	1699	2595	30403
2	GOMATI	111194	101902	-3365	0	0	6958	9747	46312
3	KHOWAI	79245	61142	-3230	0	0	3531	4366	21853
4	NORTH TRIPURA	96748	80378	-396	3213	328	1859	6961	34375
5	SEPAHIJALA	117699	100119	-18900	0	0	1293	1721	13698
6	SOUTH TRIPURA	102443	84654	5014	0	0	5719	6421	29239
7	UNAKOTI	71887	51145	6275	0	271	902	2732	29779
8	WEST TRIPURA	143787	107076	14454	2464	1083	3400	7581	57794
	Total	816751	671641	0	6077	1682	25361	42124	263453

Source: Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation, September 2015

Agartala has been ranked second in Swachh Bharat Abhiyan among the Northeastern cities. In this region Gangtok capital city of Arunachal stood first and Agartala second. All over the country Agartala is in 32nd position in Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. The survey was conducted in 2014-15 commissioned by the ministry of urban development as required under the National Sanitation Policy of 2008. The rankings of the Northeastern state capitals Gangtok (10th), Agartala (32nd), Guwahati (51st), Kohima (76th), Imphal (83rd), Shillong (120th)(GOI, 2014).

Table-1 shows the story of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan in Tripura. The initiative have not reached the approached goals but covered even wider area than set under the goal in some cases. But if we look at the overall scenario the achievements have been high till September, 2015 which certainly is a good sign for all the districts. It was observed from the table that in 4 districts i.e. Gomati, Khowai, North Tripura and Sepahijala, there are many household didn't have accesses toilet facility and in Sepahijala district it was observed more compare to other 3 districts. And it was also seen that in west Tripura district there is huge no. of uncovered household i.e. 57,794 compared to other districts.

Table: 2 Physical Progresses Reported of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan & Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) of APL & BPL Families

SL.No.	District Name	Total (APL + BPL)		
		Approved	Un.Approved	Total
1	DHALAI	1699	0	1699
2	GOMATI	6958	0	6958
3	KHOWAI	3531	0	3531
4	NORTH TRIPURA	1859	0	1859
5	SEPAHIJALA	1293	0	1293
6	SOUTH TRIPURA	5406	0	5406
7	UNAKOTI	902	0	902
8	WEST TRIPURA	3221	0	3221
	Total :-	24869	0	24869

Source: Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation, September 2015

Table-2 shows the sanitation facility of APL & BPL families in Tripura. And it is clear from the data that the appropriate proportion is completely covered, which shows the good situation of the all the district in state. The highest percentage of approval was in Gomati district i.e. 6,958. The second highest percentage in South Tripura district i.e. 5,406. The rest are as follows.

Table: 3 Physical Progresses Reported of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan & Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) of Schools:

SL.No.	District Name	School		
		Approved	Un.Approved	Total
1	DHALAI	0	0	0
2	GOMATI	23	0	23
3	KHOWAI	0	0	0
4	NORTH TRIPURA	0	0	0
5	SEPAHIJALA	0	0	0
6	SOUTH TRIPURA	0	0	0
7	UNAKOTI	1	0	1
8	WEST TRIPURA	76	0	76
	Total	100	0	100

Source: Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation, September 2015

Table 3 depicts the sanitation facility of Schools in Tripura. And it was observed that Dhalai, Khowai, North Tripura, South Tripura Districts have no approbation of Sanitation in this particular year but West Tripura have highest appropriation and also it has fulfilled its targets and then its Gomati and Unakoti District have also achieved its total percentage.

Toilets in all schools & separate toilets for girls

Fig: 5

Fig: 6

Source: DISE 2010-11, NUEPA, New Delhi

Fig 5 and fig 6 shows the status of toilets in schools and separate toilets for girl students in schools in India as well as the 3 top states of north east. It was invisible from the graph 5 that in India only 16 percentage of school are without toilet facility whereas 48 percentage of school are without girl's toilet facility. And from the graph 6 it was clearly visible, the top 3 states of north east with highest percentage of without girls toilets in schools. Manipur score the 1st position in both the case, the 2nd position are carried by Tripura and are as follows.

Table: 4 Physical Progresses Reported of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan & Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) of Anganwadi's Center:

SL.No.	District Name	Anganwadi's Centre		
		Approved	Un.Approved	Total
1	DHALAI	0	0	0
2	GOMATI	359	0	359
3	KHOWAI	394	0	394
4	NORTH TRIPURA	0	0	0
5	SEPAHIJALA	0	0	0
6	SOUTH TRIPURA	0	0	0
7	UNAKOTI	0	0	0
8	WEST TRIPURA	105	0	105
	Total :-	858	0	858

Source: Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation, September 2015

Table 4 depicts the sanitation facility of Anganwadi's Centre in Tripura. And also it is in good progress and achieving its total percentage. The highest percentage of approval is in Dhalai and Gomati District.

Table: 5 Physical Progresses Reported of Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan & Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) of Sanitary Complex:

SL.No.	District Name	Sanitary Complex		
		Approved	Un.Approved	Total
1	DHALAI	0	0	0
2	GOMATI	0	0	0
3	KHOWAI	0	0	0
4	NORTH TRIPURA	3	0	3
5	SEPAHIJALA	1	0	1
6	SOUTH TRIPURA	0	0	0
7	UNAKOTI	0	0	0
8	WEST TRIPURA	1	0	1
	Total :-	5	0	5

Source: Ministry of Drinking Water & Sanitation, September 2015

Table 5 depicts the sanitation facility of Sanitary Complex in Tripura. It is in developing stage with less percentage of approval in only 3 districts i.e. North Tripura, Sepahijala and West Tripura District. And in North Tripura District the approval is much and rest are as follows.

7. Conclusion :

In India, investments in community water supply and sanitation projects have increased steadily from the 1st plan to the 10th plan. However, the health benefits in terms of reduction in waterborne disease have not been commensurate with the investments made. Though health sector is bearing the burden of water and sanitation related infectious diseases, presently it does not have adequate institution or expertise for monitoring and surveillance of community water supply programmes in the country. India has witnessed significant improvement in rural sanitation with increasing coverage of areas and a large volume of financial resources made available. A series of schemes are aimed at improving the supply of drinking water & sanitation facility for rural habitations and now for monitoring and ensuring quality (CENSUS OF INDIA 2011, 2011).

The target on sanitation will plainly not be met unless progress is greatly accelerated, and if it is not, 600 million people will be without access to basic sanitation in 2020. Two Empowered Action Group (EAG) states e.g. Bihar and Uttar Pradesh with around 90% households with availability to improved source of drinking water have already achieved the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) target in this regard. But, in relation to sanitation, all

the EAG states (except Uttarkhand) and two developed states- Tamil Nadu and Karnataka still have a very long road to travel, despite more than doubling its provision between 1990 and 2010. According to census 2011, still around 80% population of rural EAG states are practicing open defecation. In view of very wide rural-urban differential in the provision of sanitation facilities, a particular attention needed in rural India to achieve the MDG target in this regard up to 2020. This paper has also found that households with unimproved latrine facility within premises have a higher prevalence of having diarrhoea among children U-5 than do those with improved latrine facility. So, India should raise the profile of sanitation and hygiene in all political and developmental venues to reduce the child mortality. Sanitation is in a state of crisis that needs to be addressed with due urgency (Snehalatha, 2011).

To eradicate the practice of open defecation, Gram Panchayat in rural areas and Urban Municipal Corporation or Urban Local Bodies (ULB) would need to focus not only on building infrastructure, but also on preventing open defecation through peer pressure and shame approach. There is more need for sensitization at the grass root level about the health hazards of open defecation. The relatively slow progress in sanitation when compared with that for water indicates an urgent need to pick up the pace. There is widespread acceptance that sanitation services are critical to improving health and to preserving the gains made in other sectors and a growing recognition that hygiene behaviour change is key to saving children's lives (GOI, 2011).

The study also provided some recommendations:

- i) Toilets complexes should be constructed in the markets, bus stand and community place where it is required.
- ii) Separate special strategy should be prepared for the tribal area.
- iii) There should be improvement in IEC plan (Information Education Communication plan) as because poor sanitation and open defecation was a major issue for behavior change. Continuous door to door contact with every rural household so that they can be made aware of the importance of using a toilet and the consequences of not doing so.

- iv) Launching of state level medical campaign covering audio visual, mobile telephony and local outreach programmes to communicate the message.
- v) Involvement of the various agency and organizations.
- vi) Government should collaborate with Public Private Partnerships (PPP) model, which can supplement the infrastructure deficit as well as sustainable development of rural areas. PPP can be profitably harnessed to reinforce India's position as well as Tripura's position.

References:

1. Assessing Sanitation Costs and Services in Andhra Pradesh, India. M. Snehalatha, V. Ratna Reddy, N. Jayakumar January, 2011.
2. JMP 2006.Meeting the MDG drinking water and sanitation target: the urban and rural challenge of the decade.WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation. WHO and UNICEF 2006
3. PFC 5.Progress for Children.A report card on water and sanitation. Number 5, September 2006. UNICEF
4. Implementation Manual on National Rural Water Quality Monitoring and Surveillance Programme, Department of Drinking Water Supply, Ministry of Rural Development, Govt. of India, 2004
5. CENSUS OF INDIA 2011. (2011). CENSUS OF INDIA 2011. New Delhi: Register General of India.
6. GOI. (2011). Report of the Working Group on. New Delhi: WASH Group.
7. GOI. (2014). Mission Document. Tripura: Dept. of drinking water and sanitation.
8. Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation. (2014). Swachh Bharat, Swasthh Bharat. Tripura: Department of Drinking water and Sanitation.
9. PM News Bureau. (2008). Coverage, Financing and Emerging Concerns of sanitation. New Delhi: Govt. of India.

ABOUT COLLEGE

Women's College, situated in the heart of Agartala with a total campus area of 9 acres is one of the premier institutions for women's education in Tripura. Established by the Government of Tripura in 1965, the college made a humble beginning. Initially affiliated to Calcutta University, it now enjoys affiliation under Tripura University (A Central University) and offers quality education both in Arts and Science stream. It was accredited 'B' Grade by last NAAC visit.

National seminars, conferences, workshops are organised by the College frequently. The faculty members of this College actively engage themselves in UGC sponsored Minor Research Projects. This College has an IBT Hub (Institutional Bio-Technology Hub), sponsored by the Department of Bio-Technology (DBT), Govt. of India.

ISBN-978-93-81631-37-9